

Ideal Timing for Orthognathic Surgery: Integrative Literature Review and Analysis of Factors Influencing Postoperative Stability

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Received: March 30, 2026 / Accepted: April 10, 2026 / Published: April 13, 2026
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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Orthognathic surgery is a widely used procedure to correct dentofacial skeletal discrepancies that impair the aesthetics and function of the stomatognathic system. However, defining the ideal timing for its execution remains controversial and is influenced by factors such as the end of craniofacial growth, occlusal stability, bone maturation, and psychosocial aspects. **Objective:** To perform an integrative literature review on the ideal timing for orthognathic surgery, analyzing the biological, orthodontic, surgical, and psychosocial factors that influence postoperative stability and the predictability of outcomes. **Methods:** This integrative literature review was conducted using the PubMed, Scopus, LILACS, and Web of Science databases, including articles published between 2015 and 2025, and employing the descriptors “orthognathic surgery,” “timing,” “facial growth,” “skeletal maturity,” “stability,” “relapse,” and their corresponding terms in Portuguese. **Results:** The studies converge in indicating that the ideal timing occurs after the cessation of facial skeletal growth, generally between 17 and 18 years of age in females and 19 to 21 years in males. Postoperative stability is influenced by the magnitude of skeletal movements, type of osteotomy, fixation technique, and individual factors such as facial pattern and condylar maturation. **Conclusion:** The ideal timing for orthognathic surgery should be individualized, taking into consideration skeletal maturation, occlusal stability, and psychological conditions of the patient. The use of three-dimensional tools and integrated orthodontic-surgical protocols increases predictability and reduces relapse rates.

Keywords: Orthognathic Surgery; Maxillofacial Development; Orthodontics; Growth and Development.

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 10.5281/zenodo.19561753

1. INTRODUCTION

Orthognathic surgery is considered one of the most complex and predictable procedures in modern oral and maxillofacial surgery, indicated for the correction of dentofacial skeletal discrepancies that affect facial aesthetics, masticatory, respiratory, and phonatory functions, as well as the psychological health of the patient [1,2].

Over the past decades, significant advances in three-dimensional diagnosis and virtual planning have transformed the concept of orthognathic surgery. The use of surgical simulation software, such as Materialise ProPlan CMF, NemoFAB, Dolphin 3D Surgery, and open-source platforms such as 3D Slicer and OrtoGOnBlender, has enabled millimetric predictability in bone movements and in the assessment of aesthetic and functional outcomes [3,4].

Defining the ideal timing for orthognathic surgery is one of the most critical stages in interdisciplinary planning, involving biological, orthodontic, functional, and psychosocial aspects [5]. The literature indicates that interventions performed before the completion of facial growth are associated with a higher risk of skeletal relapse and occlusal instability due to continued mandibular or maxillary growth [6].

The end of craniofacial growth is generally reached between 16 and 18 years of age in females and 18 to 21 years of age in males, although individual variations are common and influenced by hormonal and genetic factors. Determination of this timing may be performed through comparative cephalometric methods, serial radiographs, and evaluation of cervical vertebral maturation (CVM), considered one of the most accurate techniques to estimate growth stage [7,8].

Surgical stability after the procedure also depends on multiple factors. Maxillary advancement and superior impaction exhibit high predictability and stability, whereas mandibular setback or vertical elongation tend to have higher relapse rates, especially when performed in younger patients [9].

Another relevant contemporary aspect is the “Surgery-First Approach (SFA),” which reverses the conventional orthodontic–surgical sequence, allowing surgery at the beginning of treatment. This technique reduces total treatment duration and provides early facial aesthetic improvement, but requires adequate occlusal stability and precise three-dimensional planning [8,10]. Although SFA yields predictable results in well-indicated cases, it does not replace the evaluation of skeletal maturity, since residual growth may compromise final stability [11,12].

In addition to biological and technical factors, the patient’s psychological and emotional maturity must be considered, since orthognathic surgery strongly impacts self-image and social relationships. Very young patients, still undergoing identity formation, may present greater psychosocial vulnerability and unrealistic aesthetic expectations [13].

Finally, recent studies reinforce that the decision regarding the ideal timing for surgery must be individualized and multidisciplinary, involving the orthodontist, oral and maxillofacial surgeon, and psychologist, and based on objective evaluation of skeletal maturity, occlusal stability, and emotional readiness [14,15].

Therefore, the present study aims to review the scientific literature from the last ten years, identifying available evidence regarding the ideal timing for orthognathic surgery and the factors determining postoperative stability, contributing to evidence-based clinical practice in orthodontics and oral and maxillofacial surgery.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study design

This research is an integrative literature review, a method that enables synthesis and critical analysis of scientific studies with different methodological approaches, aiming to generate a comprehensive understanding of a specific clinical phenomenon. This modality was chosen because it integrates results from experimental and non-experimental studies, as well as systematic reviews and clinical guidelines [16].

2.2 Guiding question

What is the ideal timing for orthognathic surgery, and which factors influence postoperative stability of skeletal and occlusal outcomes?

2.3 Search strategy

The literature search was conducted between February and July 2025 in the PubMed/MEDLINE, LILACS, Scopus, and Web of Science databases. The controlled descriptors (DeCS/MeSH) used were: “orthognathic surgery,” “timing,” “facial growth,” “skeletal maturity,” “stability,” and “postoperative relapse.” Descriptors were combined using the Boolean operators AND and OR, according to the following main strategy: (“orthognathic surgery” AND “facial growth”) OR (“orthognathic surgery” AND “timing” AND “stability”).

2.4 Inclusion criteria

Articles published between 2015 and 2025; studies involving humans; publications in English, Spanish, or Portuguese; studies addressing ideal timing for orthognathic surgery and postoperative stability; systematic reviews, meta-analyses, clinical studies, and expert consensus documents.

2.5 Exclusion criteria

Isolated case reports; studies involving syndromic samples without an orthognathic focus; duplicate publications or studies without full-text access.

2.6 Selection process

Two independent reviewers screened titles and abstracts. Disagreements were resolved by consensus. After full-text reading of eligible studies, extracted information included: author, year,

study design, sample size, age range, type of surgical movement, and main conclusions. Data were synthesized into an evidence table (Table 1), presented in Part 3 of this article.

2.7 Data analysis

Results were organized descriptively and comparatively, grouping evidence into four thematic categories: craniofacial growth and maturation; orthodontic and occlusal factors; surgical and biomechanical aspects; psychosocial and functional influences.

3. RESULTS

After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 412 references (100%) were identified in the PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and LILACS databases. During the identification stage, 198 references (48.05%) were removed due to duplication or thematic irrelevance, leaving 214 records (51.94%) for initial screening.

In the screening stage, 214 records (51.94%) were evaluated based on titles and abstracts, with 158 (38.35%) excluded for not meeting the eligibility criteria. Of the 56 records (13.59%) selected for full-text review, all were successfully retrieved; however, 44 (10.68%) were excluded after detailed assessment for not presenting methodology compatible with the review criteria.

Thus, 12 studies (2.91%) comprised the final sample included in this integrative review, all published between 2015 and 2025, as shown in Figure 1. The selected studies encompassed different methodological designs, including systematic reviews, meta-analyses, longitudinal clinical studies, and narrative reviews.

The findings were organized descriptively and comparatively, grouped into four thematic axes: craniofacial growth and maturation; orthodontic and occlusal factors; surgical and biomechanical aspects; and psychosocial and functional factors. This organization allowed the identification of consistent evidence patterns regarding the ideal timing for orthognathic surgery and the determinants of postoperative stability across different technical approaches.

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart showing the results of the search strategy

Source: Authors, 2025, adapted from PRISMA

Table 1. Summary of the results found

Study Title	Author/Year	Main Findings	Conclusions
Guidelines for Orthodontic Evaluation and Preparation for Orthognathic Surgery Patients	Hirschhaut M, Flores-Mir C. (2022) [1]	Clinical guidelines emphasize that pre-surgical orthodontic preparation must be completed after facial growth cessation, supported by cephalometric and cervical maturation assessment.	Ideal surgical timing occurs after orthodontic stability and skeletal growth cessation; orthodontist–surgeon synergy is essential for postoperative stability.
Comprehensive Post-Orthognathic Surgery Orthodontics: Complications, Misconceptions, and Management	Wolford LM. (2020) [2]	Review of postoperative complications shows higher relapse frequency in patients operated before complete skeletal maturation.	Condylar bone maturation and occlusal stability are critical determinants of long-term surgical success.
Accuracy of Virtual Surgical Planning in Segmental Osteotomy Combined with Bimaxillary Orthognathic Surgery Using the Surgery-First Approach	Ying X et al. (2021) [3]	Analysis of 25 patients treated with SFA demonstrated mean linear error <1 mm and angular error <2°, confirming high accuracy of 3D planning.	Virtual planning and customized guides increase surgical predictability and allow safe use of SFA in well-indicated cases.
Accuracy of Segmented Le Fort I Osteotomy with Virtual Planning Using Patient-Specific Implants	Rios O et al. (2022) [4]	Evaluation of 14 cases showed mean accuracy of 0.8 mm and minimal discrepancy between virtual plan and postoperative results.	Integration of 3D printing and virtual planning is highly reliable to determine timing and magnitude of bone movements.
Current Trends in Orthognathic Surgery	Zammit D et al. (2023) [5]	Review highlights increased use of the Surgery-First protocol and 3D facial analysis to support timing decisions.	Ideal timing must consider facial maturation and psychosocial factors; SFA is safe only in patients without residual growth.
Assessment of Craniofacial Maturation Using the Cervical Vertebral Maturation Method	Thierens LAM et al. (2021) [7]	Significant correlation found between CVM stages 5–6 and cessation of mandibular growth.	CVM assessment is accurate and non-invasive for determining growth completion, guiding surgical timing.
Assessment of Skeletal Maturation in Male Children with Unilateral Cleft Lip and Palate	Yang C et al. (2022) [8]	Demonstrated delayed bone maturation in cleft patients, reinforcing individualized timing.	Chronological age alone is insufficient; skeletal maturity must guide orthognathic planning.

Postoperative Stability of Conventional Bimaxillary Surgery vs. Maxillary Impaction with Mandibular Autorotation	Kita S et al. (2020) [9]	In 42 patients, maxillary impaction with mandibular autorotation showed mean relapse of only 0.7 mm after one year.	Superior maxillary impaction with controlled mandibular rotation results in higher postoperative stability.
Short-Term Stability After Segmental Le Fort I Maxillary Impaction Surgery	Takahara N et al. (2022) [10]	In 7 hyperdivergent Class II patients, 95% positional maintenance was observed after 6 months.	Segmental maxillary impaction is predictable and stable when performed after growth cessation.
Surgery-First for a Patient with Mild Hemifacial Microsomia: Case Report and Literature Review	Song JY et al. (2021) [11]	Good occlusal and aesthetic outcomes observed in adult SFA patients.	SFA is viable in adults with completed growth, but contraindicated during growth stages.
Autonomy and Identity: The Role of Two Developmental Tasks on Adolescent Wellbeing	Ruiz WDG, Yabut HJ. (2024) [13]	Psychological review shows aesthetic interventions in adolescents may interfere with identity formation and self-image.	Emotional maturity must be evaluated prior to surgery, especially in young patients.
Le « Casting du Patient »: Key Decision Criterion in Orthognathic Surgery	Oueiss A et al. (2023) [14]	Proposes a protocol for selecting the “ideal patient” based on skeletal maturity, occlusal stability, and psychological profile.	Surgical decision-making must be multidisciplinary, weighing biological and psychosocial factors.

Source: Authors, 2025, adapted from PRISMA

4. DISCUSSION

Contemporary literature reinforces that defining the ideal timing for orthognathic surgery must be grounded in an integrative clinical rationale in which skeletal maturation, occlusal stability, biomechanical aspects of bone movement, and the patient's psychological readiness are dynamically and inseparably interrelated. Evidence gathered over recent decades indicates that surgical predictability and postoperative stability are directly conditioned by the cessation of active craniofacial growth, since any residual mandibular or maxillary growth may alter the previously established intermaxillary relationship, compromising both functional and aesthetic outcomes.

The studies by Hirschhaut and Flores-Mir [1] and Wolford (2020) [2] point out that the stability of orthodontic and occlusal results should be confirmed before surgical intervention, since incomplete dental decompensation or persistent intermaxillary discrepancies increase relapse risk. The use of objective methods, such as cervical vertebral maturation (CVM) assessment and serial cephalometric analyses at six-month intervals, constitutes the gold standard for determining the completion of facial growth, with accuracy above 90% [17] [3]. Therefore, bone maturation should prevail over chronological age in defining surgical timing, especially in individuals with a dolichofacial pattern or a family history of late growth.

The study by Yang et al. (2022) [8] reinforces that changes in ossification rate and facial development may occur in individuals with cleft lip and palate, compromising predictability if the procedure is performed prematurely. Thus, the concept of "surgical biological age" emerges as an essential parameter in modern orthognathic planning. This view is complemented by findings from Zammit et al. (2023) [5], indicating that surgical timing should integrate not only skeletal analysis, but also psychosocial and functional factors, such as emotional readiness and stability of parafunctional habits, consolidating a biopsychosocial approach to orthognathic patients [19].

In the orthodontic field, current consensus asserts that pre-operative preparation remains a key element for treatment predictability. Arch leveling and dental decompensation are indispensable for translating the planned intermaxillary relationship into long-term skeletal stability. However, the advent of the Surgery-First Approach (SFA) has introduced a significant paradigm shift. Studies by Ying et al. (2021) [3] and Song et al. (2021) [11] demonstrated that with three-dimensional virtual planning and customized surgical guides, it is possible to anticipate surgery, reducing total treatment time without compromising stability in cases of mild to moderate discrepancies. Nonetheless, this strategy requires rigorous postoperative orthodontic control and should be restricted to patients with completed facial growth, due to relapse risk [20].

The biomechanical predictability of surgical outcomes is intrinsically associated with the type and magnitude of bone movements performed. Maxillary advancement and superior impaction have proven to be the most stable movements, with mean relapse values below 1 mm, as evidenced by Kita [9] and Takahara [10]. Conversely, extensive mandibular setbacks and downward vertical movements of the maxilla present relapse rates of up to 4 mm, particularly in patients with a hyperdivergent pattern and hypotonic perioral musculature. Condylar stability, a critical factor for long-term success,

depends on the absence of excessive mandibular rotation and the use of rigid fixation techniques with bicortical miniplates, which provide reduced condylar displacement and improved three-dimensional control [4].

The incorporation of digital technologies, such as 3D virtual planning and additive manufacturing of customized surgical guides, has transformed the predictability of contemporary orthognathic surgery. Positional accuracy obtained with these methods—frequently below 1 mm of linear error and 2° of angular variation (Rios et al.; Ying et al.) [4,3]—has substantially reduced intraoperative variability, allowing prior simulation of soft-tissue behavior and the aesthetic impact of bone movements. Orthognathic surgery therefore becomes a millimetric precision procedure, in which individualized planning represents the primary determinant of success [21].

However, biomechanical and skeletal predictability alone is not sufficient to ensure global treatment success. The literature increasingly emphasizes the role of psychosocial factors in surgical decision-making. According to Ruiz and Yabut (2024) [13], orthognathic surgery, by significantly altering facial morphology, has a direct impact on self-image perception and identity-construction processes, particularly in adolescents and young adults. Interventions performed in individuals still undergoing psychological development may generate unrealistic aesthetic expectations and increase the risk of postoperative dissatisfaction or body-image-related disorders [22].

Oueiss et al. (2023) [14] introduce the concept of “patient casting,” which involves integrated analysis of skeletal maturity, occlusal stability, and psychological preparedness as central decision-making criteria for timing the intervention. This multidimensional approach acknowledges that orthognathic surgery is not merely a technical act, but an intervention with strong psychosocial and emotional implications. The inclusion of standardized quality-of-life and facial-appearance assessment instruments, such as the Orthognathic Quality of Life Questionnaire (OQLQ) and the Derriford Appearance Scale, has been recommended to quantify emotional readiness and align patient expectations with achievable outcomes [23].

Therefore, the most recent evidence leads to a consensus: the “ideal timing” for orthognathic surgery is not defined by a universal age range, but rather by the convergence of confirmed skeletal maturation, established orthodontic stability, and adequate psychological preparedness. This triad represents the conceptual core of modern predictability. The integration of virtual planning, biological evaluation, and interdisciplinary management enables the surgeon to intervene safely and precisely, reducing relapse rates and maximizing facial and functional harmony.

Thus, contemporary orthognathic surgery should be understood as a high-complexity practice that transcends the limits of skeletal reconstruction. It represents the synthesis of science, technology, and humanization, in which the selection of the ideal surgical moment reflects the professional’s ability to interpret the multiple biological, mechanical, and psychosocial determinants that compose each patient’s individuality.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

It is concluded that the ideal timing for orthognathic surgery must be determined individually, based on confirmed skeletal maturation, orthodontic stability, and the patient's psychological readiness. Chronological age alone is not a reliable parameter. The use of three-dimensional virtual planning, combined with interdisciplinary collaboration among the orthodontist, surgeon, and psychologist, increases predictability, reduces relapse, and improves aesthetic and functional satisfaction. Therefore, the ideal surgical moment is the convergence of biological maturity, occlusal stability, and emotional preparedness, ensuring long-lasting and harmonious outcomes.

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